

THE CURRENT CHALLENGES OF UPGRADING THE INFRASTRUCTURE FOR ACCESS AND PRESERVATION OF SOCIAL SCIENCE RESEARCH DATA

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- High Level Expert Group on Scientific Data report to the EC, October 2010

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

ICRI 12

16:30–18:00 Plenary Session 3

Venue: Meeting Room 1 and 3

Data: A Common Challenge

Chair: John Wood, Professor, Associate

Rapporteur: Wouter Los, Principal Scientist

International Conference on Research Infrastructures
Copenhagen, 21–23 March 2012

WWW.ICRI2012.DK

The Topic of Research data is not something new for our science community:

Načrt razvoja raziskovalnih infrastruktur 2011-2020

- The document is accepted
- The implementation already started

Korkeatasoinen ja innovatiivinen
tutkimustyö tarvitsee vahvan infrastruktuurin
Infrastruktuuryöryhmän muistio

Opetusministeriön työryhmämuistioita ja selvityksiä 2007:36

Part of a wider ESFRI framework, „the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures“.

Special financial arrangement agreed on a intergovernmental level:

Participating nations agreed on financial obligations regarding international activities and national service provision.

KAZALO

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CESSDA ERIC

- A preparations for new CESSDA ERIC were elaborated during EU fp7 project [CESSDA PPP](#)
- The expert base is defined
- Complex legal issues are being solved now:
 - we expect the formal establishment of CESSDA ERIC for beginning of 2013

CESSDA PPP goal

Creating structure

*this project is mainly about **creating a new formal legal entity** out of what has up until now been an **informal grouping**, involving organisations in different European countries. "Each of these," he said, "has **common goals of preserving and sharing data from social sciences**, and making them as readily available and as useful for users as possible – negotiating access with data producers **to increase the quantity and quality fund of data available to social scientists.** "*

*"The situation at the moment is that **the take-up**, or embracing, of data archiving, **is different in different countries**. A significant part of this project is about **promoting the role of the data archive in countries where they exist, but don't have the total buy-in from people at the top who can provide the funding needed to bring some of the less-well resourced organisations up to speed with developments that are happening elsewhere**. This will give them the opportunity to **capitalise on what others are doing - thereby effecting knowledge and skills transfer between the older and newer, the larger and smaller, organisations.***

*" Thus in **planning the new organisation**, in order to create fully interoperable systems, it will also be important to create **a more equal, accountable and sustainable funding base.**" (K. Schürer, – from the [interview](#) for [Projects 15](#) journal)*

The ADP upgrade following the National plan

Our activities in last two years:

- Organizational, human experts resources enlarged
- Trusted Digital Preservation
- Increased access to official statistical microdata for research purposes
- The ecology of consistent national policy and service infrastructure for Open Research Data is planned

Increased awareness of challenges of digital preservation

One more quote from the [Projects 15 interview](#):

Archiving is often thought of as a very **static** thing – you put something into a cupboard and then forget about it, and if somebody does want it in 100 years time then OK, they could leaf through it and glean some information. However, this can't work for digital materials.

“Instead, we **actively curate**, making sure the data are held in a format that is going to minimise possible loss. For example, so they're not dependent on software or hardware, so that in 10 years' time when that right software or equipment or storage media no longer exist or work, you haven't lost the data.”

- Granularity of different objects versions that are citable as a reference in published article:
 - DDI Study description
 - Data files: PUF, SUF, original data file with no confidentially restrictions
 - Variables
 - Related documents, files
- Persistent identifiers as infrastructure for tracing the data and publications:

See [DataCite](#)

What is DataCite?

Our aim is to:

- establish easier access to research data on the Internet
- increase acceptance of research data as legitimate, citable contributions to the scholarly record
- support data archiving that will permit results to be verified and re-purposed for future study.

Compare [**ICPSR's Efforts to Encourage Data Citation**](#)

Ongoing activity

- FP7 Project Data without Boundaries (DwB)
 - **which aim is to enhance transnational access for the researchers to government microdata within Europe through collaboration between producers of government data and data archives.**
 - The **barriers** the project addresses are those in **resource discovery, metadata standards, researcher accreditation, legal frameworks, and use of research data centres for confidential microdata.**
- SORS and ADP are contributing to different WP
- In parallel increased collaboration with SORS
 - ADP adds additional value to SORS microdata access service

CABINET OFFICE CONSULTATION ON MAKING OPEN DATA REAL

A response from the Economic and Social Data Service and the UK Data Archive

The UK Data Archive, for example, **already acts as an agent for public service providers in the dissemination of microdata produced by a number of government departments.** In over 40 years worth of activity we have maintained a balance between the commitment to ensuring data is available for research purposes while ensuring that access is controlled in accordance with the risk/impact level of the data in the disclosure of data.

The UK Data Archive, on behalf of the Economic and Social Research Council already runs the **Secure Data Service** – a unique service in the UK with a philosophy of enabling secure and safe and yet remote access to sensitive data produced by public and private sector organisations.

International incentives

// **OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding** " (2007).

Increased efficiency of science

Open research data access can help

Findings during the project

Low culture of data sharing

Policy of research data management is absent

Legal issues unsolved

Unequally developed data infrastructure and services

Report:

Opis stanja na področju raziskovalnih podatkov v Sloveniji

Accessible:

http://adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/o_arhivu/publikacije/odpp10_opis_stanja/

Main lessons learned

- Efficiency of service is an obligation: common tools development...
- Users needs are a guiding principle
- High level research policy support is necessary: explicit responsibility of service providers, research data creators and users
- Newcomers can profit

Re-using data

- follow-up research
- new research
- undertake research reviews
- scrutinise findings
- teach and learn

DEPOSIT DATA TO DATA ARCHIVES

Why deposit:

- Assurance that data meet set quality standards
- Long-term preservation of data in standardised accessible data formats
- Safe-keeping of data in a secure environment with the ability to control access
- Online resource discovery of data through data catalogues
- Licensing arrangements to acknowledge data rights
- Standardised citation mechanism to acknowledge data ownership
- Promotion of data to many users

SHARING DATA VIA DATA ARCHIVE

Benefits Of Data Sharing for Researchers

Assists in implementing publishers' data retention policies

Increases visibility of scholarly work

May enhance researchers' reputation

May increase citations (*open access journal articles cited more*)

Enable collaborations on closely related themes, and new topics

Benefits Of Data Sharing for Public

Production of high quality research with social value

Advance science to the benefit of society

Compliance with laws and regulations

Adoption of emerging norms – 'open access' publishing

To be, and appear to be, open and accountable

Benefits Of Data Sharing for Funders

Make optimal use of publicly funded research

Avoid duplication of data collection

Maximise return for investment

METADATA

A crucial part of making data **user-friendly, shareable** and with **long-lasting usability** is to ensure they can be understood and interpreted by any user. This requires clear data description, annotation, contextual information and documentation.

Good documentation for research data contains both study-level information about the research and data creation, as well as descriptions and annotations at the variable, data item or data file level.

Metadata are a subset of core data documentation, which provides standardised structured information explaining the purpose, origin, time references, geographic location, creator, access conditions and terms of use of a data collection.

[UK DA, 2012]

METADATA

Metadata for online data catalogues or discovery portals are often structured to international standards or schemes such as

Dublin Core,

ISO 11179,

Data Documentation Initiative (**DDI**),

Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard (METS) and

Statistical Data and Metadata Exchange (**SDMX**) – in NSI's.

The DDI is an international XML-based descriptive metadata standard for social science data used by most social science data archives in the world.

metadata editors

gesis

Leibniz-Institut
für Sozialwissenschaften

NSD EUROPEAN ELECTION DATABASE

CESSDA

UK • DATA
ARCHIVE

ICPSR | INTER-UNIVERSITY
CONSORTIUM FOR
POLITICAL AND
SOCIAL RESEARCH
A PARTNER IN
SOCIAL SCIENCE
RESEARCH

International research

ISSP

EUROBAROMETER

European Values Study

Atlas | European Values

European Social Survey

CSES
COMPARATIVE STUDY of ELECTORAL SYSTEMS

MPC Minnesota Population Center

SHARE
Survey of Health, Ageing
and Retirement in Europe
50+ in Europe

ACP

ACCESS TO METADATA AND DATA

Slovene social science data archives - **ADP**

SL + EN /

own services +

CESSDA portal

The CESSDA Data Portal provides a seamless interface to datasets from social science data archives across Europe. The data may be located in several ways, for example by searching or browsing by topic, keyword or data publisher. The data portal may be searched and viewed in any one of **nine languages** and through **14 EU archives**.

Most of the datasets are freely available for academic use.

- CESSDA Catalogue
 - Browse by Topic
 - DEMOGRAPHY AND POPULATION
 - ECONOMICS
 - EDUCATION
 - basic skills education
 - compulsory and pre-school education
 - educational policy
 - life-long/continuing education
 - post-compulsory education
 - teaching profession
 - vocational education
 - HEALTH
 - HISTORY
 - HOUSING AND LAND USE PLANNING
 - INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
 - LABOUR AND EMPLOYMENT
 - LAW, CRIME AND LEGAL SYSTEMS
 - NATURAL ENVIRONMENT
 - POLITICS
 - PSYCHOLOGY
 - REFERENCE AND INSTRUCTIONAL RESOU
 - SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
 - SOCIAL STRATIFICATION AND GROUPING
 - SOCIAL WELFARE POLICY AND SYSTEMS
 - SOCIETY AND CULTURE
 - TRADE, INDUSTRY AND MARKETS
 - TRANSPORT, TRAVEL AND MOBILITY
 - Browse by Keyword
 - Browse by Data Publisher
 - ADP
 - ADPSS-Sociodata
 - CDSP
 - DANS
 - DDA
 - ESS
 - FSD
 - GESIS ZACAT
 - GSDB
 - ISSDA
 - NSD
 - NSD Metadata
 - SND
 - UKDA

Search Term: **vocational education**

Study Section Variable

Study	Archive
[EUVET12] ^a 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries	ADP
Jyväskylä Longitudinal Study of Personality and Social Development (JYLS): Interviews of 27-Year-Olds 1986	FSD

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Top Terms:
 EDUCATION

Broader Terms:
 EDUCATION

Search in Specific Language:
 Lehre/Berufsausbildung (German) (3 hits)
 vocational education (English) (20 hits)
 ammatillinen koulutus (Finnish) (9 hits)

- Welfare Survey
- [EQLS03]¹ European Quality of Life Survey, 2003
- ESS - European Social Survey
- [ESWT04]¹ Establishment Survey on Working Time and Work-Life Balance, 2004-2005
- [EUACC00]³ EU Accession Opinion Survey
- EUIND - EU Index
- [EUSILC]¹ European Union survey on income and living conditions (EU-SILC)
- [EUVET12]³ 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries **NEW**
 - Metadata
 - Study Description
 - Data Files Description
 - Other Documentation
 - Variable Description
 - A: Preliminary program and the transition to the current program
 - B: Current programme
 - C: Acquired Knowledge
 - D: About yourself and your career
 - E: Acquired skills and abilities
 - F: Information and communication technology
 - G: You and your family
 - Other
 - User defined variables
 - Bookmarks
- EWCS - European Working Conditions Survey
- [FUZINE84]¹ Unexploited potential of Fužine neighbourhood
- [GOZD04]³ Conservation of nature and forest ownership - a case study of Posavje area :
- [HEBLED04]³ Attitudes of Bled residents towards HYDRO-Moste
- HRM - Human Resource Management
- ICVS - International Crime Victim Survey
- [ISJP91]² International Social Justice Project 1991
- ISSP - International Social Survey Programme
- JJM - Yugoslav Public Opinion
- JMCG - Montenegro Public Opinion
- [KAJEN06]³ Survey about passive smoking

Bibliographic Citation

Dahmen, Caroline, Brečko Barbara, Marek Fuchs and Vasja Vehovar. 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries [data file]. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Fakulteta za družbene vede = Faculty of Social Sciences, Center za družboslovno informatiko = Centre for Social Informatics [production], 2012. Slovenia, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani = University of Ljubljana, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov = Social Science Data Archives [distribution], 2012.

List of Keywords

- vocational education
- vocational programme
- knowledge
- competences
- motivation
- satisfaction
- leisure time
- work
- ICT

Topic Classification

- EDUCATION - vocational education
- Pedagogy and didactics
- Preliminary program and the transition to the current educational program
- Current educational program
- Acquired knowledge
- About you and your career
- Acquired skills and abilities
- Information and communication technologies
- You and your family

Abstract

The 7EU - VET project – Detailed Methodological Approach to Understanding the VET Education - is a research study on vocational education and training which builds on theoretical backgrounds and secondary analyses of the existing documentation as well as on national and EU data in order to conduct quantitative and qualitative studies and derive empirical results. The project is built upon one of the goals of the Lisbon strategy, which is the promotion and the quality of vocational education and training. The project addresses the following scientific and research objectives: Are educational and training systems flexible enough to adequately respond to different and changing needs? How efficient and successful are the systems (for advising and informing) and can we set up a successful model which could be implemented across the countries? What are the perceptions of the VET systems by the young people and what is their view of their future possibilities for career building and mobility? In what way are the ICT solutions implemented in vocational education programs? Stopnja opisa: 4 - Full Study description and XML DDI Codebook Data description with full questions text

ACCESS TO DATA / NESSTAR

DESCRIPTION

TABULATION

ANALYSIS

(not asked in UK)

- ▶ Current grades: overall pass_current (not asked in UK)
- ▶ Current grades: overall_comparable_current (not asked in UK)
- ▶ How would you rate this final grade in comparison to other pupils in your class?
- ▶ Study behaviour: I strive for the highest possible marks.
- ▶ Study behaviour: It is important for me to fully understand what I have to do/learn.
- ▶ Study behaviour: I want to make a good impression on my teachers by achieving good grades.
- ▶ Study behaviour: I want to make a good impression on potential employers by achieving good grades.
- ▶ Study behaviour: I want to keep up with my fellow pupils.
- ▶ **Study behaviour: I enjoy learning.**
- ▶ Study behaviour: I am interested in practical subjects.
- ▶ Study behaviour: I am interested in general subjects (e.g. maths, foreign language)
- ▶ How would you rate the amount of practical training within your programme?
- ▶ All in all, how much time in the average school week do you study outside school (e.g. homework or preparation for school)?
- ▶ Average day: Spending time with friends or peers (e.g. socialising) (not asked in UK)
- ▶ Average day: Reading books (not asked in UK)

Dataset: [EUVE12]⁹ 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries

Variable C2_6 : Study behaviour: I enjoy learning.

PreQuestion Text

Section C: Acquired Knowledge

Literal Question

C2. To what extent do you agree with the following characteristics that apply to your study behaviour? (Please tick only one box in each row) I enjoy learning.

Values	Categories	N		
1	Not at all	3747		21.6%
2	Slightly	4535		26.1%
3	Fairly	5103		29.4%
4	Quite	2553		14.7%
5	Completely	1424		8.2%
-88	not answered	265		
-77	not applicable	0		

Summary Statistics

Valid cases 17362
Missing cases 265

This variable is numeric

enjoy

Are you male or female?

Country

Country		Lithuania	Austria	Greece	Latvia	Slovenia	Germany	UK	Total
enjoy	Are you male or female?								
not	male	1,229	948	1,020	1,257	571	2,193	157	7,375
	female	673	818	613	773	479	2,183	136	5,675
enjoy	male	321	123	381	392	62	343	340	1,962
	female	264	114	329	417	32	450	320	1,926
N=		2,487	2,003	2,343	2,839	1,144	5,169	953	16,938

Choose categories - Mozilla Firefox

Go to a Web Site

Deselect all Select all Update

TREE LIST

- All
 - Lithuania
 - Austria
 - Greece
 - Latvia
 - Slovenia
 - Germany
 - UK

Type

-- Select Data Format -- Download Subset

-- Select Data Format --

- SPSS
- SPSS Portable
- Stata v.8
- Stata v.7
- Stata v.6
- NSDstat
- Statistica
- DIF
- DBase
- Textfile
- Delimited
- SAS
- Comma Separated Value

from the drop-down box.
loading.

Dataset: [EUVET12]^s 7 EU VET - Study on vocational education in seven european countries

Weight

Weighting variables defined in the dataset

Nonresponse Weigh

Weighting variables selected

>
<

Ok Clear

SEARCH
ENGINE
Search by
variable

Select appropriate weights from the list above.

If the appropriate variables are not defined as weights search the variables in the browse list. To select, click on the variable and choose 'Add as weight'. Click 'OK' to apply the selected weight(s).

Weighting information

Design weights, Nonresponse weight. When computing any tables or percentages, the design-weight should always be used. The non-response weight is the product of the design-weight and a non-response factor. Please see: <http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/podatki/euвет12/euвет12-Technicalreport.pdf>

DEVELOPMENT

URN (UNIFORM RESOURCE NAME)

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:_____

URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SURVEYID

TYPE

VERSION_REVISION

Type of materials	Suggested appendix	Example
Related materials	_RM1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RM1_V1_R1
Related publications	_RP1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_RP1_V1_R1
Other material	_OM1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_OM1_V1_R1
Data file	_D1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_D1_V1_R1
Questionnaire	_Q1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_Q1_V1_R1
Code list	_CL1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_CL1_V1_R1
Syntax	_SY1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_SY_V1_R1
Licence agreement	_LA1_V1_R1	URN:SI:LJ-UNI-FDV:ADP:SJM011_LA_V1_R1

Using two major system functions: the **URN generator** – service defining unique URN record for every object and the **URN resolver** – interpreter that connects a given URN record with a digital object.

PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

OPEN ACCESS

OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding

...are meant to apply to **research data**, whether already in existence or yet to be produced, that are supported by **public funds** for the purposes of developing publicly accessible scientific research and knowledge.....

This kind of data should be publicly available.

.. in accordance with the objectives and principles, such as openness, transparency, legal conformity, formal responsibility, professionalism, protection of intellectual property, interoperability, quality and security, efficiency, accountability and others.

UNESCO - Open Access to Scientific Information

UNESCO promotes Open Access (OA), with particular emphasis on scientific information (**journal articles, conference papers and datasets of various kinds**) emanating from publicly funded research.

**If you have questions about access to data or data archiving
please contact us at**

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

E-mail: arhiv.podatkov@fdv.uni-lj.si

